

Least-Cost Decarbonization Pathways of the Kenyan Power Sector by 2050

Energy Modelling Platform Africa (EMP-A)

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Kenya Country Context

Population: 54 Million

GDP: \$136 billion, 5th in Africa

Growth rate: 5.6% (Energy Demand)

Neighbours: Tanzania, Uganda, Somalia, Ethiopia & South Sudan

Highest Point: Mt Kenya (5,197 m)

Lowest Point: Indian Ocean (0 m)

Largest Lake: Lake Turkana (6,405 km²)

Kenya Electricity Context

Installed capacity: 3,243 MW 77% Renewable

- Geothermal: 950 MW
- Hydro: 839 MW
- Thermal/Diesel: 562 MW
- Wind: 436 MW
- Others: 412 MW

Policy Environment

- **Kenya Energy Policy 2025-2034:** commitment to 100% energy access, affordability, security, clean energy solutions, reducing fossil fuels
- **Demand Drivers:** 100% electricity & clean cooking access by 2030 and E-mobility
- **Kenya Energy Transition & Investment Plan:** commitment to Net Zero by 2050
- **Kenya's NDC** commitment reduce GHG emissions by 35% by 2035

Research Questions and Scenarios

Research Questions

- What are the least-cost energy pathways to enable Kenya achieve energy transition to Net-zero by 2050?
- What are the techno-economic trade-offs of high renewable deployment under a zero fossil fuel target?

Scenarios

Reference (BAU)
2022-2050

Unconstrained optimization (Fossil fuels allowed).

- Includes planned nuclear & geothermal for baseload
- Diesel & natural gas as peaking plants, without climate restrictions
- Demand Growth 5%
- 2022-2024 -calibrated years
- 2025-2050 forecasted years for all the scenarios.

Net Zero by 2050

Constrained: CO2 emissions to be zero by 2050

- The government prioritizes geothermal for baseload stability.
- Massive scale up of Wind & Solar.
- Storage facilities and Natural gas

100% RE by 2050

Constraint: only RE technologies are considered for investment

- Geothermal & Hydro for baseload
- Wind & Solar investments
- Storage facilities considered for energy shifting & peak load management

Reference Energy System

Results

1- Power Generation (PJ)

Power Generation: 100% RE is achievable, Net-Zero scenario, renewables supply **95%** of electricity, **50% from geothermal and NGS 5%**, while the BAU scenario continues to rely on **fossil fuels** to meet demand, Natural Gas supplying 30%

2- Power Capacity (GW)

Capacity Requirement: The Net-Zero and 100% RE scenario require approximately **14 GW** of installed capacity to meet demand due to lower average capacity factors of the Res , compared to about **10 GW** under the BAU scenario. Net-Zero Scenario invests in Natural gas. 100%RE has BESS

3- Annualized Investment Cost (MUSD)

Investment: Both Net-Zero and 100% RE require higher investments of 30% and 20%, respectively, compared to the BAU. But avoid long-term carbon lock-in and energy transition risks.

2.1- Annualized Investment Cost (MUSD)_BESS

BESS Investment: The 100% RE will require upto 50 MUSD in storage facilities for energy shifting and peak load management.

4- Projected Emissions (MTons)

Emissions: Both 100% RE and Net-Zero achieve zero carbon emissions by 2050; BAU emissions continue rising due to Natural Gas expansion.

Conclusion and Policy Consideration

Policy Alignment:

The model achieves the 100% RE in the national grid by 2040, transitioning away from fossil fuels. Both 100% RE and Net-Zero Scenarios align with Kenya`s NDC.

Net-Zero delivery requires bankable energy auctions, functioning power markets, and ancillary services that reward flexibility and low-carbon generation.

Climate-Smart Investments; the Net-Zero and 100% RE scenarios will require 30% and 20% respectively, compared to BAU. Concessional finance, climate funds, private capital and carbon markets are essential to close the Net-Zero investment gap.

Renewable-Led Capacity Expansion:

Both Net-Zero and 100% RE will require 30% than BAU to meet the increasing demand in the Kenyan power sector.

Grid Stability

A renewable-led system demands urgent grid modernisation, including storage and flexibility, to protect reliability and resilience.

Net-Zero offer more grid stability than 100% RE.

Future Research:

- **Grid studies:** 100% RE will pose grid flexibility and reliability challenges; a power system study is required.
- **Wider reach:** Expand the analysis to non-power sectors, such as Transport, Land and Agriculture.
- **Integrated investment Planning** tools such as FINPLAN across generation, transmission, and distribution.
- Assess macroeconomic, employment, and energy security impacts of Net-Zero pathways.

Asanteni & Karibu Kenya

An aerial photograph of a rugged mountain peak, likely Mount Kenya, covered in snow. The mountain's ridges and valleys are clearly defined, with the snow appearing in various shades of white and light blue. The surrounding landscape is a vast, open plain under a clear blue sky. The text 'Asanteni & Karibu Kenya' is overlaid at the top in a black, sans-serif font.

Thank You